

Research Paper

Engineering a Galinstan-based ferromagnetic fluid for heat management

J.P. Maganinho^a, R.M.C. Pinto^a, V. Andrade^{a,b}, B.G.F. Eggert^d, C. Frommen^d, J.P. Araújo^a, J.O. Ventura^a, J. Oliveira^c, A.L. Pires^{a,*}, J.H. Belo^{a,*}

^a IFIMUP - Institute of Physics for Advanced Materials, Nanotechnology and Photonics, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Faculty of Sciences of University of Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre, 687, 4169-007 Porto, Portugal

^b Brazilian Centre for Research in Physics (CBCF), Rua Xavier Sigaud 150, 22290-180 Urca, RJ, Brazil

^c Associate Laboratory for Energy, Transports and Aerospace (LAETA/INEGI), Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

^d Department for Hydrogen Technology, Institute for Energy Technology (IFE), P.O. Box 40, NO-2027 Kjeller, Norway

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ABSTRACT

The development of increasingly smaller electronic devices brings on heat dissipation challenges, which can severely hinder their performance. Consequently, there is a critical need to maintain the working temperature of these devices at optimal values. At room temperature, the versatile design and adaptability of fluidic thermal switches makes them an auspicious solution. In this work, the large heat conductivity and magnetic material compatibility of Galinstan motivated the production of a novel ferromagnetic fluid. Through mechanical alloying within an inert atmosphere, we embedded Ni microparticles in a Galinstan matrix, which provided a liquid metal with a ferromagnetic behavior. This fluid is suitable for a wide range of applications in thermal management. Here, we experimentally demonstrate that a Galinstan-based mixture containing 2.6 wt% of Ni can serve as heat exchange medium in a magnetically activated fluidic thermal switch device. This mixture establishes an optimal thermal bridge between heat source and sink, enabling heat dissipation from the source. This effect intensifies with the device operating frequency, reaching a maximum temperature span of 19.8 % and a maximum switching ratio of 1.26. These results demonstrate the potential of the developed fluid to be integrated into fluidic technologies for temperature control of electronic components.

1. Introduction

Advancements in modern technology have been intrinsically linked to the development of increasingly smaller devices, which inevitably imply higher thermal power densities [1,2]. Conventional thermal management methods are unable to maintain the optimal temperature values for these systems. This has led to a growing interest in new thermal control devices (TCDs) to enable effective heat flux control. By adjusting their thermal resistance, TCDs boost heat dissipation and prevent overheating [3–7]. These devices can be solid-state, where there are no moving parts and the operation depends on the phase transition of phase change materials [8], or fluidic. For the latter case, when the conductive path between heat source and sink is formed, the interface thermal resistance is reduced in comparison to solid-state TCDs [5,9,10]. As a consequence, there is an enhancement in the heat flux across the contact surface [2]. In addition, these fluidic TCDs benefit from an increased adaptability, which offers new design possibilities.

Table 1 summarizes some thermophysical properties of fluids

typically used in thermal applications. For fluidic TCDs, the thermal conductivity of the working fluid is a critical operating parameter [1]. For applications around room temperature, as depicted in Table 1, conventional liquids (such as water and ethylene glycol) have substantially lower thermal conductivities than those of liquid metals (LMs). Therefore, the incorporation of LMs into novel heat dissipation technologies holds great potential [11–13]. The most well-known room temperature LM, used in many daily applications, such as thermometers and electromechanical relays, is Mercury [14]. However, the toxicity of Mercury has motivated research on other alternatives [15]. Gallium-based alloys emerge as one of the most promising alternatives. Gallium has the lowest melting point among the post-transition metals, being around 30 °C. Still, benefiting from the high solubility of Gallium (Ga), Indium (In) and Tin (Sn) within each other, it is possible to reduce this temperature down to 11 °C, by forming a monophasic alloy known as Galinstan [16]. This LM is renowned for its low vapor pressure (< 10⁻⁶ Pa at 500 °C), high boiling point, high thermal and electrical conductivity, as well as its chemical compatibility with several materials

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: ana.pires@fc.up.pt (A.L. Pires), jbelo@fc.up.pt (J.H. Belo).

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[14,17]. The standard composition for Galinstan is Ga/In/Sn (68:22:10) wt.% [18]. Deviating from this value can change the baseline thermal properties of the alloy, specifically its thermal conductivity, which lies within $(24 \pm 1) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ [17,19,20]. Notably, these values are more than 38 times greater than that of water - $(0.607 \pm 0.004) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ [21].

The thermophysical properties of Galinstan have favored its investigation for incorporation in conductive circuitry applications over the last 15 years [15,22,23]. In fact, this technology is already employed for CPU cooling by companies like ASUS [24] and Sony [25], demonstrating its maturity. Moreover, innovative prototypes for LM-based CPU cooling, such as the one proposed by Deng *et al.* [26] have demonstrated competitive performance with commercially available alternatives. This illustrates the immense potential for the incorporation of Galinstan in cooling technologies. Furthermore, the literature reports the utilization of Galinstan in TCDs. In the study conducted by Yang *et al.* [9,27], is proposed the incorporation of Galinstan droplets within channels filled with NaOH, with the objective of creating an electrically actuated thermal switch (EATS). The authors report the ability to actively control a heat flux of 15 Wcm^{-2} at a switching ratio (SR) of 2, and with a switching time of 5 s. However, this timescale is not feasible for the typical frequency range required in TCDs' applications. In this context, the control of Galinstan with magnetic fields would be more promising, given that magnetically actuated thermal switches (MATSS) are reported to have the fastest switching response [1,28].

In addition to its favorable thermophysical properties, Galinstan can be successfully endowed with magnetic properties [29]. As evidenced in Table 2, in previous research, different magnetic particles have been added into Galinstan to produce different magnetic LMs. For instance, Castro *et al.* [18] successfully manually alloyed micrometer-sized Gadolinium (Gd) particles into Galinstan to produce magnetic LM composites containing up to 2.3 wt.% of Gd. Additionally, Xiaokang *et al.* [23] were able to produce magnetic Galinstan droplets with Fe and NdFeB particles. This attribute broadens Galinstan's range of applications, making it suitable for incorporation in fluidic TCDs, particularly in MATS devices, that can be wireless and remotely controlled by external magnetic fields. These novel devices benefit from their precise and fast ability to control switching states with different thermal conductivities. To the best of our knowledge, there are currently no reports in the literature of the incorporation of Galinstan-based magnetic LMs in MATS devices. Nevertheless, the utilization of different ferrofluids in these devices has yielded promising results [3,4,6,10,30]. For example, Shi *et al.* [6] achieved a temperature span of 22.6 % using a Fe_3O_4 -based ferrofluid and a heating power of 14.4 W. In a separate study conducted by Rodrigues *et al.* [4], using an identical magnetic fluid, a maximum temperature span of 44.4 % was attained for a heating power of 39 W. Furthermore,

Andrade *et al.* [3] have reported a MATS system based on MnFe_2O_4

nanoparticles dispersed in an Ethylene Glycol:Water solution. In this study, for a heating power of 0.42 W, temperature spans and SRs up to 60 % and 7, respectively, were achieved. However, the reported devices suffer from fluid vaporization issues, due to the low boiling points of the base fluids, which diminishes the device durability. This would not be the case for Galinstan, due to its high boiling point. In addition, their thermal conductivities are lower than that of Galinstan. These two features motivated this work, as their combination suggests a promising utilization of Galinstan-based magnetic LMs in MATS devices.

Following this approach, in the present work, a ferromagnetic fluid, which synergistically combines the large heat conductivity of Galinstan with the ferromagnetism of Nickel (Ni), was developed. Compared to iron-based fluids, nickel-based ones are expected to offer greater cost-effectiveness for long-term applications, as Ni is less prone to oxidation due to its lower reduction potential [31]. In the literature, there are already reports of Ni nanoparticles being mixed into Gallium and the EGaln alloy, which require a silica coating previous to preparation in air atmosphere [32]. In this study, uncoated micron-sized Ni particles are mixed into a Galinstan matrix within a controlled atmosphere. This constitutes a simpler and faster preparation method which enables a larger-scale production of the magnetic fluid. The fluid was tested in a MATS prototype. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of the feasibility of a Galinstan-based ferromagnetic fluid in heat management control applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fabrication of Ni microparticles

Ferromagnetic Ni microparticles were produced by mechanically grinding a Ni bulk piece (99.9 + % purity, purchased from Alfa Aesar) with a steel file, followed by two hours of orbital ball milling in a Mini-Mill PULVERISETTE 23. The milling was performed at a vertically oscillating frequency of 50 Hz, with zirconium oxide balls at a ball-to-powder ratio of 2.6:1.

2.2. Fabrication of the Galinstan

Galinstan was synthesized using Gallium, Indium and Tin purchased from Alfa Aesar (Ga, In) and Thermo Scientific (Sn) with 99.99 % of purity. The setup used to produce the Galinstan is depicted in Fig. 1 (a). The first step in fabricating the Ga/In/Sn (68:22:10) wt.% (target composition) alloy was to determine the target batch mass. Subsequently, the mass of each precursor was calculated based on the desired final composition.

After being weighed on an analytical balance, the reagents were transferred to a glass beaker. To synthesize the alloy, the beaker was heated up in a sand bath within a steel pan, using a hot plate as the heat

Table 1

Thermophysical properties of fluids suitable for applications in fluidic thermal control devices. Except for those specifically identified, the values were obtained at room temperature conditions. [12,16–21,33,34].

Fluid	Water	Ethylene glycol	Mercury	Gallium	EGaln	Galinstan
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.607 ^a	0.258	8.34 ^b	29.4 ^c	26.58 ^d	23.03 – 25.25
Heat capacity ($\text{kJ m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$)	4183	2659	1883 ^b	2186 ^c	2556 ^d	1874 – 2481
Melting point (°C)	0	-12.6	-38.87	29.8	16	10.6 – 13.2
Boiling point (°C)	100	197.2	356.65	2204.8	>1300	>1300
Density (kg m^{-3})	998 ^e	1132	13546 ^b	5907 ^c	6280 ^d	6360 – 6440
Dynamic viscosity (mPa s)	1.002	9	1.50 – 1.83	2.0	1.69 – 2.50	1.89 – 2.40 ^f
Surface tension (mN m^{-1})	72.8 ^d	48.4	455 ^b	707 ^c	624 ^d	587 – 605 ^d
References	[12,21,33,34]	[12]	[12,33,34]	[12,33,34]	[12,19,34]	[16–20,34]

^a at 25 °C and 0.1 MPa.

^b at 25 °C.

^c at 50 °C.

^d at 20 °C.

^e at 35 °C.

Table 2
Characteristics of reported Gallium-based ferromagnetic fluids. [18,23,32,35].

Ferromagnetic fluid	Particle size	Magnetic material wt. %	Particle treatment	Type of structure	Production method	References
Galinstan + Gd	425 μm	0.2 – 2.3	none	fluid	Mechanical alloying in a N_2 atmosphere	[18]
Galinstan + Fe	6 μm	–	none	droplets	5 min stirring of the mixture in air and surface treatment	[23]
Galinstan + NdFeB	8 μm and 15 μm	–	none	droplets	with HCl	
Gallium + Fe	9 μm	33	none	fluid	no information	[35]
Gallium + Ni	1 μm	33	none	fluid		
	nanoparticles	10	SiO_2 coating	fluid	60 min stirring of the mixture in air	[32]
EGaIn + Ni	nanoparticles	5 and 10	SiO_2 coating	fluid		

Fig. 1. Illustration of the setups used to produce Galinstan (a) and ferromagnetic fluid (b) batches. In subfigure (a): H, hot plate; S, steel pan; R, glass rod; T, digital thermometer. In subfigure (b): G, Aldrich® AtmosBag glove bag; M, mortar, and pestle; E, set of clean, filled with liquid metal and filled with Ni powder Eppendorf tubes; P, Pasteur pipettes; N, NdFeB magnets.

source with the temperature kept above the highest melting point of the elements (231.9 °C for Sn [36]). During the melting process, the mixture was stirred with a glass rod until becoming completely liquid, as reported by [18].

2.3. Fabrication of the ferromagnetic fluid

The ferromagnetic fluid results from the combination of Galinstan and Ni particles. The batches of the ferromagnetic fluid were produced using the setup depicted in Fig. 1 (b).

The fabrication of each batch started by filling and weighing a 2 mL Eppendorf recipient with Galinstan. Then, the Ni powder was weighed to match the target magnetic material concentration. The mixture of Ni particles into the Galinstan matrix was made inside an Aldrich® AtmosBag glove bag with a four-time purged inert Ar atmosphere. The ferromagnetic material was mixed in the liquid metal using an agate mortar and pestle until the mixture became homogeneous [18]. Finally, the magnetic susceptibility of the fluid was pre-evaluated by observing its response to the presence of permanent magnets. These tests are demonstrated in videos V1 and V2 in the Supplementary Information (SI).

2.4. Material characterization

To analyze their morphology and chemical composition, the samples were inspected by room-temperature Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) combined with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). The SEM/EDS setup used in this study was FEI Quanta 400FEG ESEM / EDAX Genesis X4M.

To evaluate the transition temperatures (associated with chemical composition) of the Galinstan samples, Differential Scanning

Calorimetry (DSC) [TA Instruments® DSC25 calorimeter] was used, together with alumina sample holders. The samples' temperature was cycled between – 100 °C and 100 °C at a constant rate of 10 °C/min.

The thermal conductivity of the Galinstan and ferromagnetic fluid samples was indirectly determined through measurement of their electrical resistivity, using the four-point probe technique, and application of the Wiedemann-Franz law approximation [37]. This approach allows for the determination of the thermal conductivity with an accuracy of 1–10 % [37]. The measurements were performed in a home-made setup, which is presented in Section 2 of the SI, along with the considered methodology.

The crystalline structure of the Ni powder was evaluated through room-temperature X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements using a Rigaku SmartLab Diffractometer (Cu – α , 45 kV and 200 mA) in Bragg-Brentano geometry. The Ni powder was placed on top of a Si (100) substrate and the data were acquired with a 0.01° step for the $2\theta \in [30^\circ, 110^\circ]$ interval.

A MPMS 3 SQUID Magnetometer was used to measure the magnetization of the Ni microparticles, the Galinstan and the ferromagnetic fluid for different magnetic fields, ranging from – 5 T to 5 T, at a fixed temperature of 300 K. The Ni magnetic powder measurements were corrected according to the protocol proposed by Amorim et al. [38].

2.5. MATS proof-of-principle method

The performance of the ferromagnetic fluid was evaluated in a home-made magnetically actuated thermal switch (MATS) setup, as reported in [10,39], and illustrated in Fig. 2 (a) and (b). As depicted in Fig. 2 (b), the ferromagnetic fluid is stored inside a cylindrical container made of Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), with 1 × 1 cm height and diameter. On its top and bottom surfaces, two copper plates – thermally

Fig. 2. (a) Illustration of the setup used in the experiments conducted with the developed ferromagnetic fluid incorporated into the magnetically actuated thermal switch (MATS), with the device outlined by the dashed box. (b) Schematic of the device used and its operating states (ON and OFF). [10].

Fig. 3. SEM top-view of the Ni powder with $500 \times$ magnification and obtained in backscattered mode and histogram of the corresponding particle size distribution (inset).

conductive windows for the heat source (bottom) and sink (top) – are physically attached to the cage with non-magnetic screws.

As can be seen from the setup of Fig. 2 (a), the fluid is controlled by applying an external magnetic field. The field variation is promoted by the vertical periodical movement of a set of nine $20 \times 20 \times 3$ mm NdFeB block magnets purchased from Supermagnete. As measured using a Lakeshore 455 DSP gaussmeter placed at the top surface of the container, the field intensity varies periodically between 12 and 438 mT (magnets at the top and bottom position of their range of motion, respectively).

The device operates between two states, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (b). In the OFF state, the magnetic field strength is insufficient to overcome the gravitational force and the fluid remains only in contact with the heat source – a Peltier element (TEC112706, 12 V). In the ON state, as the strength of the applied magnetic field increases, the fluid is attracted to the magnets, creating a thermal bridge with the heat sink – a copper plate in contact with the ambient. Video demonstrations of the MATS operation at low (Video V3) and high (Video V4) frequency are available in SI. These videos illustrate the cyclical formation and breaking of the thermal bridge, as the MATS transitions between its ON and OFF states. The temperature of the heat source and heat sink terminals is monitored using two thermocouples (TCs), which are attached to the conductive windows using thermal paste and copper tape. Additionally, the ambient temperature is measured with another thermocouple. These TCs are connected to a TC-08 thermocouple data logger (Pico Technology), and the data acquisition is controlled by a home-made software.

The device starts operating when the heat source reaches a constant temperature value ($T_{\text{source}}^{\text{start}}$) during the heating process. This phenomenon triggers the motor, starting the magnets vertical movement at a predefined frequency during a certain time span. Following this period, the device is cooled using an electrical fan. All these processes are fully automated with custom-developed software programs.

3. Experimental results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the Ni microparticles

In Fig. 3 is depicted the SEM image obtained to analyze the size and morphology of the produced Ni particles. It is possible to observe particles with an irregular shape and a broad particle size distribution. These characteristics are typically associated with top-down processes such as the ones used here [40,41].

Using the software ImageJ, we estimated the size of each particle in the image (approximately 300 in total) and obtained the particle size histogram shown as inset in Fig. 3. This histogram illustrates the profile of the fitted size distribution, which follows a log-normal function, characteristic of particles that went through mechanical grinding and milling [40,42]. From the parameters obtained after fitting their size distribution, a mean particle size of $(16 \pm 8) \mu\text{m}$ was estimated.

Fig. 4 (a) presents the X-ray diffractogram of the produced Ni particles at room temperature, ranging $2\theta = 30^\circ - 110^\circ$. Several Bragg peaks can be seen in this diffractogram, denoting the polycrystalline nature of the produced powder. The observed peaks were indexed to the Ni structure, specifically at $2\theta = 44.5^\circ$ (111), 51.9° (200), 76.4° (220), 93.0° (311) and 98.4° (222). No additional phases were detected, showing that the mechanical grinding and ball milling did not change the crystallographic structure. In this context, structural Le Bail refinements were carried out using the FullProf software [43]. The refinement, considering a face centered cubic phase (Fm $\bar{3}$ m space group) yielded a lattice parameter of 3.5 \AA and a unit cell volume of 43 \AA^3 , in accordance with Bradley et al. [44].

The magnetization hysteresis curve at 300 K is represented in Fig. 4 (b), demonstrating the ferromagnetic response of the particles. From the experimental data it was possible to determine a saturation magnetization of $(58.9 \pm 0.2) \text{ Am}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$, which is close to the values reported by

Crangle et al. [45]. Additionally, the Ni particles show no exchange bias and have a coercive field of $(6.3 \pm 0.1) \text{ mT}$. This low coercivity not only favors their utilization in high frequency applications, due to the intrinsic smaller heat dissipation in each hysteretic cycle, but, most importantly, also reduces the cluster formation probability of the magnetic particles.

3.2. Characterization of the Galinstan

The chemical composition of the Galinstan batch was measured through EDS. Within the intrinsic uncertainty of these measurements, we obtained the target Ga/In/Sn (68:22:10) wt.% composition.

In Fig. 5 is depicted the DSC scan of the produced Galinstan batch, in the temperature interval from -100°C to 100°C . The endothermic peak during heating (whose onset occurs at P_1) signals the melting of the alloy. The three exothermic peaks during cooling (with onsets at P_2 , P_3 and P_4) are indicative of a multiple step solidification process. From that figure, it is also notorious the supercooling behavior of the alloy, with clearly distinct melting and solidification temperatures, as previously reported in [18,19,34,46].

Concerning the melting of the alloy, the obtained melting temperature, $T_{P_1} = 9.8^\circ\text{C}$, is slightly lower than previously documented values, which range from 10.6°C to 13.2°C [18,19,46]. The inset in Fig. 5 illustrates the zoom-in on this phase transition, showing that it rather corresponds to the superposition of two peaks. This phenomenon has already been reported in the literature with the appearance not only of partially overlapped peaks [19], but also of a completely bimodal peak structure [46], when considering a lower heating rate.

On cooling, the observed stepwise solidification process is expected for the Galinstan sample, since it is characteristic of alloys made from materials with significantly different melting points [46]. The peak P_2 which onsets at $T_{P_2} = 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ can be attributed to small-scale solidification processes, namely to the nucleation of Sn₂-like clusters [19]. The peaks P_3 and P_4 whose onset occur at $T_{P_3} = -49.2^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{P_4} = -75.3^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, are indicative of the solidification of different metal phases at different temperatures. Still, these phase change temperatures are much lower than already documented ones. While for P_3 the reported values lie within -30.5°C and -26.4°C , for P_4 they can range from -38.5°C to -35.8°C [19,46]. This deviation can be explained by the contribution of the Ga₂O₃ nanometer-thick layer that forms around Galinstan as it makes contact with air [15]. This oxide layer works as a barrier to the heterogeneous nucleation observed during solidification, which enhances the supercooling effect of the sample [47].

The electrical resistivity of the Galinstan sample was measured using the four-point probe technique and the setup disclosed in Figure S1 of the SI. Figures S2 (a) and (b) illustrate the results from the voltage (V) and temperature (T) measurements for each applied electrical current (I), in each measurement mode. From the slope obtained after fitting the V(I) data to a linear regression, and considering Ohm's law, it was possible to determine an experimental electrical resistivity value of $(2.850 \pm 0.004) \times 10^{-7} \Omega\text{m}$. This value is slightly smaller than those reported by Handschuh-Wang et al. [34], which lie within the range $[2.89, 3.04] \times 10^{-7} \Omega\text{m}$. Regarding the T(I) measurements, it was possible to calculate the experiment's mean temperature value. Combining the obtained value with the expression for the Wiedemann-Franz law [37], the thermal conductivity of the sample was determined. An experimental value of $(25.50 \pm 0.04) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ was obtained, which is slightly higher than those previously reported - $(24 \pm 1) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ [17,19,20] - as depicted in Table 1.

3.3. Characterization of the ferromagnetic fluid

In Fig. 6 (a) is depicted the SEM image of the ferromagnetic fluid. From this figure it is possible to observe two distinct zones: zone Z1, corresponding to the Galinstan matrix and zone Z2, showing a Ni piece

Fig. 4. (a) X-ray diffractogram of Ni microparticles showing the experimental (I_{exp} – orange circles) and the Le Bail refined (I_{calc} – black line) data, along with the expected Miller indexes for each reflection (vertical pink lines). The difference between the experimental and refined data ($I_{exp} - I_{calc}$) is also represented by the green line. (b) Ferromagnetic response of the Ni particles to varying applied magnetic fields in the range $[-5, 5]$ T, at 300 K. The inset corresponds to a zoom-in of the low-field range between -50 mT and 50 mT.

Fig. 5. Thermogram obtained for a Galinstan sample with the endothermic (P1) and exothermic (P2, P3 and P4) transitions identified. The inset corresponds to a zoom-in of the melting transition associated to P1.

incorporated in the liquid metal base. This illustrates the nature of the produced fluid: during the fabrication process, instead of dissolving in Galinstan, the Ni particles were embedded into the liquid metal, forming nucleation sites with the liquid metal wrapping the magnetic particles.

The ferromagnetic fluid's magnetization as a function of applied magnetic field curve results at 300 K are illustrated in Fig. 6 (b). At this temperature, the major contribution to the magnetization comes from Ni, since its magnetic susceptibility is orders of magnitude larger than that of the diamagnetic Galinstan matrix (as confirmed by the magnetization curve of Galinstan at 300 K depicted in Figure S4 in SI). Consequently, the incorporation of the Ni particles provides the mixture with a ferromagnetic behavior. The ratio between the saturation magnetization of the fluid and the saturation value of Ni at 300 K should account for the wt. % of Ni in the mixture. Hence, from the experimental data, it was possible to calculate a fluid Ni concentration of 2.6 wt%.

The results of the electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity characterization of the ferromagnetic fluid are depicted in Figures S3 (a) and (b), in SI. Following the methodology previously outlined for the Galinstan sample, an experimental electrical resistivity value of $(3.437 \pm 0.008) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ was determined. This value was combined with the experiment's average temperature to determine the thermal conductivity of the ferromagnetic fluid. The experimental value calculated using the Wiedemann-Franz law [37] was $(21.22 \pm 0.05) \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, which is slightly lower than that of the Galinstan sample. This can be attributed to the oxidation induced by the mixing of the Ni particles within the Galinstan matrix, during the fabrication process of the ferromagnetic fluid [48]. The greater oxide content of the ferromagnetic fluid also translates into a decrease in wettability, as evidenced by the higher contact angle of the fluid droplet, in comparison to a Galinstan droplet, as illustrated in Figures S5 (a) and (b) of the SI.

3.4. Thermal switch experiments

To demonstrate the feasibility of the ferromagnetic fluid produced in this work, the previously described MATS prototype was used. The influence of the loading filling ratio (FR), i.e. the volume percentage occupied by the ferromagnetic fluid inside the cylindrical container, and the frequency of the magnets' vertical motion (operating frequency) on the performance of the device were studied. With that purpose, for each FR (65 % and 85 %), several operating frequencies (0.014 Hz, 0.05 Hz, 0.1 Hz and 0.5 Hz) were tested.

In Fig. 7 (a), for a FR of 65 %, it is illustrated the temperature variation of the heat source and sink during a complete trial. Each trial comprises three steps: heating up until the heat source reaches a constant temperature value ($T_{\text{source}}^{\text{start}}$), device operating (at a specific operating frequency, 0.05 Hz in this case) and cooling.

In Fig. 7 (b) it is emphasized the effect of the thermal switch operation on the temperature difference between source and sink ($\Delta T^{\text{so-si}} = T_{\text{source}} - T_{\text{sink}}$). As can be seen from the inserted plot representing the first 100 s of operation, in the ON state (high-field state) there is a decrease in $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$. This indicates that the heat produced by the source is exchanged through the fluid and absorbed by the sink, as illustrated in Fig. 7 (c). In the OFF state (low-field state), the previously absorbed heat is released by the sink, thus decreasing its temperature (T_{sink}) and, consequently, increasing $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$. Nevertheless, the cycle overall variation in $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ is negative, since the $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ decrease in the ON state overmatches its increase in the OFF state. As a result, the sequential occurrence of these cycles ends up resulting in a decrease of the average temperature difference with time. This behavior was manifested in every trial, which highlights the proof of principle of a ferromagnetic fluid-based MATS.

To evaluate the influence of the experimental parameters on the performance of the MATS device, a set of figures of merit is considered. Firstly, it is considered the evolution of the temperature span (ΔT_s) with operating time (t), given by:

$$\Delta T_s(t) = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta T(t)}{\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}(0)}\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}(0)$ corresponds to the starting value of $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ and $\Delta T(t)$ is the value of $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ averaged over a cycle centered at time t . The higher the value of this figure of merit, the larger is the decrease of the temperature gradient between the heat source and heat sink, in comparison to its initial value. In addition, it is also considered the minimum $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ rate achieved in each trial. This value corresponds to the minimum of the derivative of $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ with respect to the operating time. The more negative the value of $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ rate is, the more efficient is the sink's heat absorption. Furthermore, the switching ratio (SR), as defined by Eq. (2), is taken into consideration. This parameter quantifies the enhancement in the device's effective thermal conductivity during its operation ($k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ON}}$), in comparison to its value when deactivated ($k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{OFF}}$). To calculate $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ON}}$ and $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{OFF}}$, the system was modeled as a stationary one-dimensional thermal circuit. The details of this model are presented and explained in greater depth in Section 5 of the SI. Finally, to quantify the heat flux dissipation through the sink (ϕ_{sink}), the same model was considered. The value of ϕ_{sink} obtained in each trial was calculated using Eq. (3), where $\Delta T_f^{\text{so-si}}$ is the value of $\Delta T^{\text{so-si}}$ at the end of the MATS operation, and L is the thickness of the MATS ($L = 1 \text{ cm}$).

$$\text{SR} = \frac{k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ON}}}{k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{OFF}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_{\text{sink}} = \frac{k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ON}}}{L} \Delta T_f^{\text{so-si}} \quad (3)$$

Concerning the influence of the FR on the MATS performance, from the plots in Fig. 8 (a), it is clear that, despite the similar ΔT_s time dependence for both FRs, at each operating frequency, higher ΔT_s values were achieved for a FR of 65 %. This effect is primarily related to the longer ON state time spans experienced for this FR. The MATS is in the ON state during the time period in which a thermal bridge is established between the heat source and heat sink terminals by the ferromagnetic fluid. At a specific operating frequency, the time dependence of the magnetic field is identical for both FRs, as the movement of the magnets is identical. However, the magnetic field strength required to attract the ferromagnetic fluid and establish the thermal bridge is higher for the 85 % FR, due to the larger volume of fluid that must be attracted. Consequently, the time period in which the magnetic field satisfies this condition will be reduced. To illustrate, when an operating frequency of 0.014 Hz is considered, for a FR of 85 %, the transfer of heat between the heat source and sink, and through the ferromagnetic fluid, occurs on average during 13 s in each cycle. In contrast, for a FR of 65 %,

Fig. 6. (a) SEM top-view of the Galinstan and Ni (2.6) wt.% fluid with 2000 × magnification and obtained in backscattered mode. (b) Magnetic response of the Galinstan and Ni (2.6) wt.% fluid to varying magnetic fields in the range [−5, 5] T, at 300 K. The inset corresponds to a zoom-in of the low-field range between −50 mT and 50 mT.

this thermal connection lasts, on average, 17 s per cycle. These ON state time span differences are illustrated in Figure S7 in SI. This phenomenon culminates in a greater heat dissipation from the source, precisely, for the 65 % FR. This conclusion is corroborated by the higher values of SR and ϕ_{sink} yielded for the 65 % FR across all tested frequencies, as depicted in the plots in Fig. 8 (b) and (c), respectively.

Considering the plots depicted in Fig. 8 (a), it is imperative to

elucidate the considerable uncertainty associated with the ΔT_S values at 0.014 Hz frequency. At this frequency, the duration of the heat rejection (OFF state) and absorption (ON state) periods is longer. Consequently, the temperature fluctuations within each cycle are more pronounced, resulting in a higher standard deviation for each ΔT_S .

To evaluate the effect of the operating frequency, in Fig. 8 (d) is depicted the temperature span obtained after 550s of device operation,

Fig. 7. (a) Illustration of the temperature variation of the heat source (solid red line) and heat sink (solid blue line) throughout a complete trial, for a filling ratio of 65 % and a magnet movement of 0.05 Hz frequency. The red and blue dashed lines identify the temperature values of the heat source (T_{source}^{start}) and heat sink (T_{sink}^{start}) at the start of the device operation, respectively. The subplot on the right corresponds to a zoom-in of the period of device operation. (b) Temperature difference between source and sink (ΔT_{so-si}) time dependence during the device operation, in the same trial. The subplot identifies the different operating states of the device. (c) Diagrams illustrating the fluid shape in each operating state and its relation to the high and low heat exchange between both terminals.

for every frequency tested, when considering a FR of 65 %. From there, it becomes clear that, for longer operating times, there is a tendency for ΔT_S to increase with frequency. This is mostly due to the enhancement of the number of heat exchange cycles between the two surfaces. Nevertheless, this increase in the temperature span with the operating frequency is expected to be verified only until a certain frequency threshold (f_{TH}), as previously observed by Puga *et al.* [10]. Above this threshold, due to its viscosity, the fluid does not have time to make a thermal bridge between the heat source and heat sink terminals. Consequently, the obtained temperature spans will be smaller than the ones achieved for frequencies below f_{TH} .

In light of the aforementioned phenomena, it is possible to conclude that the tested ferromagnetic fluid-based MATS device exhibited optimal performance for a FR of 65 % and an operating frequency of 0.5 Hz. Under these working conditions, the MATS achieved a maximum ΔT_S value of 19.8 %, a minimum ΔT_{so-si} rate of -0.27 °C/s, and a SR of 1.26. This resulted in a ϕ_{sink} of 560 Wm^{-2} , corresponding to a heat dissipation efficiency of 62.4 %. As stated by Klinar *et al.* [1], the most appropriate metric for performance comparison in thermal switches is the SR. Therefore, under these optimal working conditions, the MATS device demonstrated superior performance compared to the results reported by Shi *et al.* [6] and by Sütterlin *et al.* [30], where Fe_3O_4 -based ferrofluids were employed as working fluid, with maximum values for SR of 1.12 and 1.04, respectively. In contrast, the $MnFe_2O_4$ -based MATS device developed by Andrade *et al.* [3] attained a maximum SR of 7.33 for a fully filled 3 cm-thick device and an operating frequency of 0.3 Hz. The latter yielded a notable improvement in performance in comparison to our work, primarily due to the significant enhancement in k_{eff}^{ON} , resulting from the magnetically-induced anisotropy, which aligned the magnetic particles along the field direction to thermally connect the

heat source and heat sink. Nevertheless, the lower boiling point of the $MnFe_2O_4$ -based working fluid, in comparison to Galinstan (>1300 °C [16–20,34]), suggests that the Galinstan-based MATS device may operate for a longer period of time at the same performance level.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we developed and characterized a ferromagnetic fluid that combines the excellent heat conduction properties of Galinstan (experimental thermal conductivity of (25.50 ± 0.04) $Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$) with the ferromagnetism of Ni. As disclosed by its room-temperature magnetic curve, the mixture, with a Ni concentration of 2.6 wt.%, exhibits ferromagnetic behavior, which demonstrates that it can be remotely controlled through application of an external magnetic field. This was successfully achieved while considering a fabrication procedure that required no additional treatment of the liquid metal and the magnetic particles, thereby facilitating a larger-scale production, in comparison to previously reported methods.

To test the fluid's viability for thermal applications, the Galinstan-based mixture was introduced into a MATS system. Our findings revealed that, for each of the tested magnet movement frequencies and FRs, the device demonstrated effective control of the heat flux between heat source and sink. The MATS heat dissipation was maximum for the lower FR (65 %) and higher frequency (0.5 Hz) tested. Under these optimal working conditions, a temperature span of 19.8 % and a switching ratio of 1.26 were achieved. As far as we are concerned, this represents the first demonstration of the feasibility of a Galinstan-based ferromagnetic fluid for use in magnetically actuated TCDs.

Further studies with different concentrations of magnetic material could be addressed to determine the concentration that optimizes the

Fig. 8. (a) Temperature span (ΔT_s , as defined in Eq. (1)) time evolution for the FRs and operating frequencies tested on the MATS. (b) and (c) Switching ratio (SR) and heat flux dissipation through the sink (ϕ_{sink}) obtained for each FR and operating frequency tested, respectively. (d) Temperature span obtained after 550 s of MATS operation, at a FR of 65 %, for every operating frequency tested.

performance of the fluid, in terms of magnetic and thermal transport properties. This strategy aims to fully leverage the advantages of the thermal conductivity of the Galinstan, thereby facilitating the development of an effective remote and wireless technology for managing the thermal conditions of electronic components, with a longer-lasting performance than currently available magnetically actuated alternatives.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

J.P. Maganinho: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **R.M.C. Pinto:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **V. Andrade:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **B.G.F. Eggert:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **C. Frommen:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **J.P. Araújo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **J.O. Ventura:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **J. Oliveira:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **A.L. Pires:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **J.H. Belo:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.119130>.

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